

Poly-Sorb: Synthesis of Waste-Derived Polysulfide Sorbents for Oil Spill Recovery and Environmental Remediation

Osorio Lolo iii, Daniel Adrian Labadan, Ginrie P. Villaruel, Kathrina Clariss P. Duliente,
Jesson H. Cinto

Carlos P. Garcia Senior High School
Juan Luna Street, Poblacion District, Davao City

Abstract - This study utilized sulfur, waste cooking canola oil (WCCO), and sodium chloride, a waste-derived polysulfide sorbent synthesized for potential use in oil spill recovery and remediation. Through thermal copolymerization at 170°C, washed, and dried. Three concentrations were produced (15–15–70, 20–20–60, and 25–25–50 wt%). Oil absorption capacity, reusability retention across three cycles, and oil removal efficiency were tested for the three concentrations of polysulfide sorbent. Based on the findings, all concentrations showed successful results in absorbing oil, with 15-15-70 wt% achieving the highest mean absorption (1.42 g/g) and reusability retention (38.73%). 25-25-50 wt% performed the highest in terms of oil removal efficiency (96.0%), followed by 15-15-70 wt% (95.0%). Among three different concentrations, one-way ANOVA showed no statistically significant difference at $\alpha = 0.05$ in terms of absorption capacity. The polysulfide sorbent showed effective absorption, moderate reusability, and high removal efficiency generally, indicating for its potential as a low-cost and eco-friendly sorbent. To help improve durability and performance, enhancement and conducting extended testing under simulated environmental conditions are recommended for future studies.

Keywords: Polysulfide sorbent, waste cooking oil, oil spill recovery, absorption capacity, reusability, oil spill remediation

I. INTRODUCTION

Oil spills happen where hydrocarbons, typically in liquid form like diesel and heavy fuel oil, unintentionally enter environments. Such incidents typically occur within coastal marine regions. Overall cases were primarily related to industrial pollution, contaminated vessels, coastal leaks, and ruptured storage tanks. Which caused dreadful ecological consequences such as contamination of surface and groundwater, halting fishing and tourism, and devastation of fish and other related species. Recreational activities affected by the gulf states impacted by Deepwater Horizon include boat fishing and beach-going experiences like swimming, surfing, and wildlife viewing. Due to oiling and cleanup activities, some beaches and recreational fisheries were closed. It casts a negative light not only on the negligence of fossil fuel usage but also on the urgency for innovations and alternatives to render them economically viable (National Ocean Service, 2024).

Oil spills harm marine life and coastal communities through pollution and economic change making it a major global environmental hazard. A storage tank for fuel at Norilsk-Taimyr Energy's Thermal Power Plant No. 3 burst on May 29, 2020, affecting an immediate area of 18 hectares (44 acres), the

nearby Daldykan River, contaminating an area of 350 square kilometers (140 square miles) caused the approximately 17,500 tons spill of diesel oil into local rivers. A total of \$1.5 billion dollars clean-up cost and estimated that emergency relief program would sustain a cost of \$146 million (Admin, 2024). In addition, Sainato (2023) elaborates on the Keystone pipeline, said to go 2,600 miles in length from Canada to the US, and has been noted to leak 14,000 barrels of oil into a Kansas creek. In 12 years, the pipeline has encountered 22 oil spills. As a result, dead animals recovered from the spill site such as four mammals and 71 fish. Initial cleanup efforts were implemented where about 5,500 barrels of oil and 5,000 cubic yards of oil-contaminated soil have been recovered.

In the Philippines, several major oil spills have devastated the ecosystems. On July 25, 2024, the tanker MT Terra Nova capsized and sank in the waters off Bataan, Philippines, with its load of 1.4 million liters of industrial fuel oil affecting its surrounding environment (Rogayan et al., 2024). Moreover, Agaton et al. (2023) indicated that oil spill that happened in the waters of Oriental Mindoro, MT Princess Empress an oil tanker carrying 5660 bbl. of industrial fuel oil sank off and adjacent provinces resulted in the damaging of 21 marine protected areas, including seagrass beds, mangroves, and fish larvae pathways. The spillage caused 6603 liters of oily water, 113 drums of waste from shoreline clean-up, and 1276 sacks of oil-

contaminated debris. 166 barangays and 172,928 people from MIMAROPA, Regions VI, and CALABARZON were affected.

In Davao City, clean-up operation for an oil was conducted by the Philippine Coast Guard. Spill booms and absorbent pads were laid out, recovering 30 liters of sludge oil (Macairan, 2024). The spill reached up to 200 cubic meters results in contamination of coastal waters and harm marine life. The Coast Guard implemented memorandum circulars prohibiting oil dumping in the sea, and violators faced administrative fines and local laws (GMA Integrated News, 2024).

Despite advancements in oil spill remediation, lab-developed sorbents only have limited research on how it be scaled for wider use, particularly by small-scale industries and communities with limited access to technology and resources. According to Zaarour and Liu (2023), many lab-developed sorbents show high absorption capacities but their performance in large-scale spills or harsh marine environments is untested. Furthermore, effective disposal and recycling of current synthetic sorbents such as polyurethane foam waste become imperative (Elnaz Zarezadeh et al. 2024). In addition, microplastics breaking down posed environmental concerns from synthetic sorbents breaking down that require proper disposal after absorbing oil (Absorbents Online, 2024).

To address this gap, the researchers wanted to synthesize a polysulfide sorbent made from waste cooking canola oil (WCCO) as a potential oil spill sorbent. By repurposing WCCO, helps reduce environmental waste and provide low-cost alternatives to conventional sorbents. This presents a major solution for oil spill clean-up and promotes sustainable resource management by making use of waste material and its cost-effectiveness, contributes to more sustainable environmental management practices, making it suitable for worldwide adoption.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This research sought to develop a polysulfide sorbent made from Waste Cooking Canola Oil for oil spill recovery, emphasizing sustainability. Particularly, it sought to answer the following questions:

What is the mean oil absorption capacity of the polysulfide sorbent, considering the following concentrations:

- Sulfur (15 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (15 wt%), Salt (70 wt%);
- Sulfur (20 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (20 wt%), Salt (60 wt%); and

- Sulfur (25 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (25 wt%), Salt (50 wt%)?

What is the mean reusability retention of the polysulfide sorbent, considering the following concentrations:

- Sulfur (15 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (15 wt%), Salt (70 wt%);
- Sulfur (20 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (20 wt%), Salt (60 wt%); and
- Sulfur (25 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (25 wt%), Salt (50 wt%)?

What is the oil removal efficiency from the oil-water mixture by the polysulfide sorbent at the following concentrations:

- Sulfur (15 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (15 wt%), Salt (70 wt%);
- Sulfur (20 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (20 wt%), Salt (60 wt%); and
- Sulfur (25 wt%), Waste Cooking Canola Oil (25 wt%), Salt (50 wt%)?

Is there a significant difference among the different concentrations of polysulfide sorbent in terms of absorption capacity?

Research Hypothesis

This study will be tested at .05 level of significance.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the absorption capacity among the different concentrations of polysulfide sorbent.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

With its interconnection with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Number 14: Life Below Water, which advocates for the conservation, and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and marine resources, this study aligns with the global efforts to protect the aquatic ecosystems from possible pollutants and degradation. The development of a low-cost, renewable and sustainable polysulfide sorbent synthesized from waste cooking canola oil, offers an environmentally friendly solution to mitigate the environmental impact of oil spill. This study holds significance for stakeholders, this includes fishermen, residents, government agencies, policymakers and future researchers.

Fishermen. This study aimed to provide an eco-friendly solution for quick oil spill clean-up to help improve biodiversity in the ocean, restore fishing grounds for fishermen and protect marine ecosystems. By using this polysulfide

sorbent, many fishermen can benefit from a cleaner water and increase catching fish.

Residents. This study could benefit residents, particularly in coastal areas, by addressing environmental, economic, and health issues related to oil spills. Additionally, this study provides efficient and sustainable solutions for oil spill clean-up, safeguarding coastal waters to stay clean and safe for local communities that depend their lives on food and livelihood.

Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR). This study benefits BFAR by providing a sustainable and alternative solution to traditional clean-up method for oil spills. This line up to BFAR's aim to protect and sustain the aquatic resources of the country while supporting responsible environmental practices.

Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR). This study benefits them by utilizing it to improve the oil spill management, helping them protect our marine ecosystem and environment. Additionally, this study can provide eco-friendly clean-up strategies for oil spill clean-up.

Policy Makers. This study can help policymakers to promote an eco-friendly solution and help support marine resource preservation and environmental protection. They can mitigate by implementing hazardous clean-up method and alternatives by promoting policies encouraging usage of sustainable materials such as polysulfide sorbent and promote renewable practices using waste practices such as waste cooking canola oil and enhance oil spill preparedness and response agenda.

Future Researchers. This study would provide clear reference on the synthesis of polysulfide sorbent using sulfur powder, waste cooking canola oil and salt. Performance against oil spills from the findings on optimal concentration may guide further improvements in sorbents composition, testing procedures, and development of more sustainable oil absorption materials.

IV. SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This research aimed to investigate and observe the copolymerization process and to help determine the sorbent's oil absorption capacity and reusability made from waste cooking canola oil for oil spill cleanup under controlled laboratory conditions.

The researcher conducted the experiments in controlled settings and are limited to laboratory testing and are not involved in a real-world application such as marine environments. Performance in actual seawater conditions was not covered in this study and factors such as large-scale deployment, long-term environmental impact, and performance in actual seawater conditions were not covered.

V. DEFINITION OF TERMS

The following terms were defined based on this study:

Absorption Capacity refers to the amount of used engine oil absorbed by the sorbent per unit mass (g/g) by each of the concentration of the polysulfide sorbent during tests.

Reusability refers to the polysulfide sorbent's ability to retain oil absorption performance over multiple sorption-desorption cycles and is evaluated by measuring the absorption capacity change after repeated oil absorption and recovery processes.

Concentration refers to the specific weight percentage formulations of polysulfide sorbent, which are 15-15-70 wt%, 25-25-50 wt%, and 20-20-60 wt%—corresponding to sulfur, WCCO, and salt, respectively.

Weight Percentage (wt%) refers to the proportion of sulfur, WCCO, and salt used in each sorbent concentration, reported as 15-15-70 wt%, 25-25-50 wt%, and 20-20-60 wt%.

VI. METHODS

This section presents the methodology of the study, which consists of four (4) main phases: phase I – Gathering and Preparation of materials; phase II – Synthesis of the Polysulfide Sorbent; phase III – Parameter Testing; phase IV - Comparative Oil Absorption Testing.

VII. RESEARCH DESIGN

An experimental-quantitative research design was utilized in this study to collect data and information. According to Knight (2010) as cited in Sirisilla (2023) researchers use experimental research design so that researchers can more effectively carry

out their research aims. Allowing an exact description of the findings gives readers a better understanding of the data collection process and appropriate experimental design acts as a roadmap for research techniques.

For testing of the effectiveness of the polysulfide sorbent in oil spill absorption, experimental design was chosen in this study

for controlled testing. This method provides precise and measurable data on polysulfide's sorbent performance by systematically manipulating and measuring the polysulfide's absorption capacity. By using quantitative design, helps provide reliable results that are important in practical application of the polysulfide sorbent in environmental cleanup because it deals with statistical analysis and numerical measurements to determine the polysulfide sorbent's efficiency in absorbing oils spills. Furthermore, to create a clear and cause-and-effect relationship, experimental approach is important between the polysulfide sorbent and its capabilities in oil spill remediation.

Gathering and Preparation of Materials for the Polysulfide Sorbent

Gathering of Materials

To ensure accuracy and efficiency, the synthesis of the polysulfide sorbent needed specific materials. Sulfur powder was ordered on August 18, 2025, and received on August 24, 2025. Sodium Chloride (NaCl) was bought on August 30, 2025. Waste cooking canola oil (WCCO) was gathered from household sources on August 30, 2025. Used engine oil was taken as the absorbate to replicate oil spill conditions and to test for absorption capability.

Preparations

Filtering process was implied to ensure the purity and consistency before utilizing the waste cooking canola oil (WCCO) in synthesizing the polysulfide sorbent. The collected waste cooking canola oil was strained to help remove large particles. Additionally, allowing the oil to settle also helps heavier impurities to sink on the bottom

Synthesis of Polysulfide Sorbent

The researcher adapted the procedure in synthesizing polysulfide sorbent from a study conducted by Worthington et al. (2018).

These were the following procedures:

- Heated sulfur (3g, 15 wt%) to 170 °C with constant magnetic stirring until the sulfur was completely melted and turned from solid to yellowish liquid.
- Added waste cooking oil (3g, 15 wt%) with constant magnetic stirring.
- Added the salt (14g, 70 wt%) to the molten mixture after 10 minutes and further stirred at 170 °C.
- Removed the flask from heat after the mixture turned solid and cooled to room temperature.
- Cooled the mixture for 1 hour until it became dark brown colored solid.
- 6.Purified the mixture by washing with water to remove NaCl.

- 7.The purified product was then dried for 12 hours.
- 8.Dried the purified product for 12 hours.

Parameter Testing

Absorption Capacity Testing:To determine the absorption capacity of the polysulfide sorbent, static soaking gravimetric method was used. One (1) gram of the synthesized polysulfide sorbent was let to absorb used engine oil for one (1) minute. Then, it was removed and allowed to drain in a strainer for five (5) minutes and was weighed. The sorbent was measured in grams per oil over grams of sorbent (g/g) and was calculated using the formula below to identify absorption capacity:

$$\text{Absorption Capacity} = \frac{W_f - W_i}{W_i}$$

Where:

$$W_f = \text{final mass of oil-soaked sorbent}$$

$$W_i = \text{sorbent's initial dry mass}$$

Reusability Retention Testing: Testing the reusability retention of the polysulfide sorbent evaluates its ability to still absorb oil when used repeatedly. The absorption capacity of the first cycle (C_1) was noted by following the first absorption and weighing:

$$C_1 = W_t - W_i$$

To remove the oil that was absorbed by the polysulfide sorbent, simple mechanical pressing was utilized. The sorbent was drained again to get rid of the remaining oil before it was used again. The absorption capacity (C_n) was measured after performing three (3) consecutive cycles using the same gravimetric method that had been described earlier. The reusability was expressed as the percentage of absorption capacity retained after three (3) cycle n, and was calculated using the equation below:

$$\text{Retention (\%)} = \frac{C_n}{C_1} \times 100$$

Where:

$$C_1 = \text{absorption capacity during the first cycle}$$

$$C_n = \text{absorption capacity during the n-th cycle}$$

The mean retention was calculated as the average percentage of the second and third cycles in relation to the first cycle to assess the overall performance of each concentration, and the formula below was used:

$$\text{Mean Retention (\%)} = \frac{\frac{C_2 + C_3}{2}}{C_1} \times 100$$

Oil Removal Efficiency Testing

The sample was sent to laboratory for testing. Specifically, SMEWW 5520 B was utilized to extract oil from water and identify the oil removal efficiency after the absorption of used engine oil on water. This method was applied to accurately identify the amount of oil that remained in the water after the absorption process which helped assess the polysulfide sorbent's efficiency to remove oil from oil-water mixture. Furthermore, 1 gram of first replicate of the polysulfide sorbent was used on an oil-water mixture containing 1 gram of used engine oil in this analysis, and different sorbent concentrations such as 15-15-70 wt%, 20-20-60 wt% and 25-25-50 wt% were tested to compare their oil removal performance. Formulation below was used:

Oil Removed = Initial Oil – Residual Oil

$$\text{Removal Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Oil Removed}}{\text{Initial Oil}} \times 100$$

Comparative Oil Absorption Capacity Testing

A comparative test was performed in this study. The absorption capacity was applied to the three (3) replicates of the different concentration of the polysulfide sorbent. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was carried out to test whether there are significant differences in oil absorption capacity among the different concentrations of the polysulfide sorbent.

15-15-70 wt% Concentration

To confirm reliability and effectiveness of this formulation, it was replicated three (3) times and was evaluated regarding its absorption capacity when using used engine oil as an absorbate. The first (1st) concentration of polysulfide sorbent was synthesized using sulfur (3g, 15 wt%), waste cooking canola oil (3g, 15 wt%), and sodium chloride (14g, 70 wt%).

20-20-60 wt% Concentration

To confirm reliability and effectiveness of this formulation, it was replicated three (3) times and was evaluated regarding its absorption capacity when using used engine oil as an absorbate. The second (2nd) concentration of polysulfide sorbent was synthesized using sulfur (4g, 20 wt%), waste cooking canola oil (4g, 20 wt%), and sodium chloride (12g, 60 wt%).

25-25-50 wt% Concentration

To confirm reliability and effectiveness of this formulation, it was replicated three (3) times and was evaluated regarding its absorption capacity when using used engine oil as an absorbate.

The third (3rd) concentration of polysulfide sorbent was synthesized using sulfur (5g, 25 wt%), waste cooking canola oil (5g, 25 wt%), and sodium chloride (10g, 50 wt%).

VIII. WASTE DISPOSAL

All materials which sustained damage, the debris, and by-products that were generated during the synthesis of polysulfide sorbent from waste cooking canola oil were sealed in an appropriate container with proper markings. The researcher made certain that hazardous waste put away in containers included excess sulfur residues and unreacted chemicals. Waste materials are forwarded to the Material Recovery Facility at Barangay 28-C, Davao City, for proper disposal. Recyclable materials, including excess used cooking oil and uncontaminated laboratory glassware, were recycled.

Data Analysis

The statistical tests that were carried out to further analyze the data are as follows:

Mean. For each of the three (3) replicates for each of the concentration, the average reusability retention and absorption capacity was taken

Percentage. With the help of this test, the performance of each concentration of the synthesized polysulfide sorbent was expressed in proportion, thus, it aided in identifying which concentration has the highest efficiency, concerning reusability retention and the oil removal efficiency.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This test helps indicate whether different concentration has a significant effect on the absorption capacity and helps determine whether the observed difference in mean values was statistically significant or not.

IX. RESULTS

This section presents the polysulfide sorbents oil absorption capacity, reusability retention, and the oil removal efficiency of the polysulfide sorbent. Oil absorption capacity (g/g), reusability (% retention) over three consecutive cycles and oil removal efficiency are the important performance parameters in the discussion section. Analysis data were conducted and comparisons among the three concentrations with different concentrations of sulfur, WCCO, and sodium chloride : 15-15-70 wt%, 20-20-60 wt%, and 25-25-50 wt%.

Oil Absorption Capacity

The measure of the amount of oil absorbed per mass unit of the dry sorbent (g/g) is the absorption capacity. The average oil absorption capacity (g/g) of the three concentrations is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Absorption Capacity

Concentration (wt%)	Replicate 1 (g/g)	Replicate 2 (g/g)	Replicate 3 (g/g)	Mean (g/g)
15-15-70	0.74	1.56	1.95	1.42
20-20-60	0.62	1.37	1.79	1.26
25-25-50	0.66	1.42	1.69	1.26

15-15-70 has the highest mean absorption capacity among the three concentrations (1.42 g/g) while 20-20-60 and 25-25-70 share the same mean value (1.26 g/g). The results indicate that changing the sulfur, Waste Cooking Canola Oil (WCCO), and salt (NaCl) concentrations affects different polysulfide sorbents overall absorption behavior.

Reusability Retention of the Polysulfide Sorbents

Reusability retention evaluation was done by measuring the absorption capacity throughout three cycles, whereby draining and oil recovery were conducted between each cycle. The retention (%) per cycle and the mean retention (%) across the reused cycles are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Reusability Retention

Concentration (wt%)	1 st Cycle (%)	2 nd Cycle (%)	3 rd Cycle (%)	Mean Retention (%)
15-15-70	100%	47.18%	30.28%	38.73%
20-20-60	100%	45.24%	23.02%	34.13%
25-25-50	100%	40.48%	31.75%	36.11%

The 15-15-70 concentration was the most noteworthy in terms of mean retention, that is 38.73%, which means that this concentration also had the greatest oil absorption capacity. On the other hand, the 20-20-60 concentration shows mean retention of only 34.13%. The three concentrations showed moderate reusability and show decreasing performance in each successive cycle.

Oil Content Analysis

The analysis involved extracting and measuring the used engine oil that remained in the water samples after the absorption process with the treatment of polysulfide sorbent. The initial oil concentration, residual oil concentration, oil removed, and removal efficiency (%) for each concentration are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Oil Content Analysis

Concentration (wt%)	Initial Oil Concentration (g)	Residual Oil Concentration (g)	Oil Removed (g)	Removal Efficiency (%)
15-15-70	1.00	0.05	0.95	95.0
20-20-60	1.00	0.11	0.89	89.0
25-25-50	1.00	0.04	0.96	96.0

All different concentrations of polysulfide sorbent showed high oil removal efficiency. Among all concentrations, the 25-25-50 concentration has the highest oil removal efficiency of 96.0% compared to other concentrations. Meanwhile, 20-20-60 concentration recorded the lowest efficiency at 89.0%.

Comparative Statistical Analysis

A one-way ANOVA was conducted for both absorption capacity and reusability to see if the seen differences between the concentrations were statistically significant or not. Shown in Table 4 below is the computed full Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the mean oil absorption capacity at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

Table 4. Absorption Capacity ANOVA

Source	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	0.050163	2	0.025081	0.0739	0.9296	Not significant
Within Groups	2.035933	6	0.339322	-	-	-
Total	2.086096	8	-	-	-	-

The ANOVA test results show an F-value of 0.0739 and a p-value of 0.9296 at a 0.05 level of significance. Since the p-value is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This means that among the three polysulfide sorbent concentrations indicate no statistically significant difference in the mean oil absorption capacity.

X. DISCUSSION

The performance of polysulfide sorbent derived from waste cooking canola oil for oil spill recovery and its findings in this study reveal valuable insights. It was found that while differences in measured oil absorption capacity and reusability exist numerically through comparative evaluation of the three concentrations with varying sulfur, waste cooking canola oil, and salt contents, these differences in measured oil were found statistically insignificant based on the ANOVA results at the 0.05 level of significance.

The polysulfide sorbent with the concentration 15–15–70 wt% (S–WCCO–NaCl) shows the highest mean oil absorption capacity (1.42 g/g) among the three concentrations. On the other hand, the other two concentration which is 20–20–60 wt% and 25–25–50 wt%, share the similar mean capabilities (1.26 g/g), implies that adding the sulfur and oil content beyond 15 wt% does not further improve the sorption capacity of the sorbent. Furthermore, this shows that lower sulfur and oil concentration combined with higher salt proportion have contributed to a more porous matrix, enhancing the oil uptake. This finding is supported by Ren et al. (2021) states that with a balanced low sulfur, moderate oil, and higher salt content shows enhanced oil hydrocarbon uptake performance due to

easier diffusion into interconnected pores that resulting in porous polysulfide. Additionally, the ability of the sorbent to absorb oil efficiently is affected due to excessive sulfur cross-linking which reduces flexibility and limit pore accessibility (Shao et al., 2016). Moreover, the synthesis process successfully produced stable polysulfide networks, regardless of concentration differences which are suggested by the consistent performance across all concentrations, which is supported by Abdullah (2023) stating that mechanical stability as well as surface morphology remained constant despite differences in sulfur concentration.

Assessing sustainability and practicality of sorbent materials helps determine both cost-effectiveness and environmental viability, that is why reusability is one of the crucial and important parameters. Gradual decline in retention (%) with each of the reuse cycles was revealed by the results. The 15–15–70 wt% concentration again showed the highest mean retention (38.73%), followed by 25–25–50 wt% (36.11%) and 20–20–60 wt% (34.13%) concentrations. A balanced combination of sulfur, oil and salt components may help maintain structural integrity during repeated use suggested by the pattern shown. Pore blockage, structural compaction, and residual oil remaining in the sorbent matrix after drying was attributed to the decline in retention across cycles. Decrease of available surface area for absorbing new oil caused by pore blockage when residual oil or contaminants get trapped inside the pores after sorption and incomplete recovery (Wang et al., 2023). Considerable portion of their capacity was retained by the sorbent, aligning with the study of Taha et al. (2023), showing that polysulfide can be reused and often maintaining more than 30% of their original sorption capacity.

All the concentrations of the polysulfide sorbent showed effective removal of used engine oil from oil-water mixture. The 25–25–50 concentration has the highest efficiency (96.0%) while the 20–20–60 concentration resulted in lowest oil removal efficiency (86.0%). Overall, the findings showed that the polysulfide sorbent derived from waste cooking canola oil can serve as an effective and eco-friendly alternative oil spill sorbent. Polysulfide sorbent has a high affinity for hydrocarbons due to the hydrophobic nature of sulfur and waste cooking oil components where it can effectively remove oil from seawater, making it suitable for mitigating oil spill pollution in aquatic environments (Flinders University, 2018).

Evaluating whether the observed differences among the concentrations are significant using one-way ANOVA results providing statistical basis. In mean absorption capacities, the computed F-value (0.0739) was lower than the p-value (0.9296) at the 0.05 significance level, indicating that there

were no statistically significant differences. Ren et al. (2021) mentioned that changes in oil absorption through reuse cycles do not produce meaningful changes where statistical analyses often reveal the reasonable variations to sulfur-to-oil ratios.

XI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the conclusions that were from the results and findings of the study. Furthermore, this section offers recommendations as to how the results and findings can further improve the study.

Conclusions

- The following conclusions are drawn by the researcher based on the findings of the study:
- 1. With the varying concentration of sulfur, WCCO, and sodium chloride (15–15–70, 20–20–60, and 25–25–50 wt%) for potential application in oil spill remediation, this study successfully synthesized and evaluated the polysulfide sorbents. Additionally, it was shown that lower oil sulfur and oil ratio coupled with higher salt content promotes better porosity and oil uptake efficiency, with the 15-15-70 composition exhibiting the highest mean oil absorption capacity of 1.42 g/g. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that all concentrations effectively absorbed oil.
- 2. Among the three concentrations, the 15-15-70 concentration also achieved the highest mean retention value of 38.73%, suggesting a more stable and reusable sorbent compared to the others. Furthermore, reusability tests attributed to pore blockage, structural compaction, and residual oil accumulation revealed a gradual decline in oil retention.
- 3. All polysulfide sorbent concentrations showed high oil removal efficiency based on the oil content analysis using SMEWW 5520 B ranging from 89.0% to 96.0%. These findings confirm that the synthesized polysulfide sorbent can effectively remove used engine oil from oil-water mixture which supports their potential for oil spill recovery application.
- 4. Using one-way ANOVA statistical analysis, the three concentrations were not statistically significant showing $p > 0.05$, implies that the synthesis process produced relative consistent polysulfide sorbent networks across all compositions, confirming variations of the oil absorption capacity.

Recommendations

- The following recommendations are given based on the conclusions presented:
- To help improve the mechanical strength, surface area, and reusability of the polysulfide sorbents, incorporating reinforcing fillers such as activated carbon, silica, or biochar is recommended. To enhance the selective oil affinity, surface functionalization with hydrophobic agents can be applied.
- Evaluating the performance of the polysulfide sorbent using various oil types such as crude oil, diesel, or lubricant oils is recommended. Additionally, it is recommended to test the polysulfide sorbent under different environmental conditions like temperature, salinity, and agitation to simulate real-world oil spill scenarios.
- Conducting life cycle and cost-benefit analysis would help identify the overall sustainability and commercial viability of the polysulfide sorbent compared to conventional oil spill sorbent materials.
- To validate the practical effectiveness of the sorbents in real oil spill recovery operations, pilot-scale synthesis and field testing are recommended to assess large-scale production feasibility.
- To determine the optimal balance that maximizes both oil absorption capacity and reusability, future researchers may explore different ratios of sulfur, type of waste cooking oil, and salt. Additionally, to enhance pore uniformity and structural stability, they may adjust salt proportion or introduce alternative porogens. Furthermore, to minimize pore blockage and retain higher absorption capacity over multiple cycles, further research should focus on improving sorbent recovery and regeneration methods such as solvent washing.
- Only the first replicate for each concentration of the polysulfide sorbent was tested for oil removal efficiency, it is recommended that future studies analyze multiple replicates per formulation. This will confirm whether the observed efficiencies remain consistent across multiple trials and help provide stronger statistical validity and minimize experimental bias.

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